

Use case factsheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Decision makers				x		
Officers/technicians			x	x	x	
Researchers	x	x		x	x	
General Public				x		
xxx						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	ZGZ-UHI
Name	Urban Heat Islands
Description	Based on the estimation of urban hotspots, a refined visualisation service aims to identify and calculate vulnerability indicators. This service incorporates existing data from external partners, such as information on individuals affected by tropical nights, as well as citizen input collected to gauge perceived temperature levels. A visualisation and download service will be available to present these data, harmonised with vocabularies and data models, together with other information, aiming to influence citizens’ awareness and behaviour. It will enable technicians and administrators to download, process, and combine different data sources for analysis and solution proposals. Finally, decision-makers can then use these data to take appropriate alleviating measures, such as designing climate shelters.
Primary User	Decision makers, citizens, technicians
Goal	To identify the location of urban heat islands (UHI) hot spots at the city level; make UHI monitoring service and the related data available to the public; and support planning interventions to mitigate their effects.

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

Owner	<i>Oficina Técnica de Transparencia y Gobierno Abierto, Department of Geography - University of Zaragoza</i>
Status	<i>Under development</i>
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	<i>Zaragoza grapples with the risk of extreme temperatures and high seasonal variations. Every year, a new record on the number of tropical nights is registered. On a tropical night, the minimum temperature remains above 20°C. This trend indicates a growing number of extreme heat events, which pose significant health risks, particularly in the context of high emissions levels.</i>
Strategy/Plan/Regulation	<p><u>Strategy for Climate Change, Air Quality and Health (ECAZ 3.0)</u>, is the first major policy instrument designed to coordinate climate mitigation actions. Together with the Climate City Contract (CCC) these two cross-sector initiatives promote mitigation measures that aim to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Line of Action 1 regarding urban design promotes increasing urban green infrastructure to reduce paved surfaces, mitigate UHI effects, and enhance vegetation's role as a carbon sink, thereby regulating the carbon cycle. <p>Zaragoza <u>Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2030 (#PACCZ 2030)</u>. PACCZ 2030 is the second iteration of the PACES 2030 in terms of adaptation, as it presents an update of the Risk and Vulnerabilities Assessment and includes an adaptation action plan composed by 9 areas (human health, water and hydrological resources, green infrastructure and biodiversity, agriculture and food, urban planning and energy, mobility and transport, education and society, research and innovation and other productive sectors) and 46 actions.</p> <p>The plan identifies Action Areas 3, 5, and 7 that contain measures around green infrastructure, urban planning, and mobility to mitigate the UHI effect. Moreover, the transversal Action Areas 7 and 8 on education and research aim to strengthen community engagement by providing robust information and promote experimentation in the field of adaptation.</p>
Local Green Deal / City contract(s)	<i>In the Climate City Contract, Pillar 3 promotes actions on re-naturalisation and circular economy. The use case can contribute to the identification and characterisation of UHI, and support among other things the city's plan to expand green areas, forests and tree stands to achieve a 5 to 7% reduction in the total emissions generated in Zaragoza.</i>
European Green Deal Policy Area	<i>This use case contributes to increasing the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; and achieving the priorities related to climate adaptation. The EU Strategy for Adaptation sets both the framework for achieving climate neutrality and the ambition on adaptation by 2050. The implementation of these actions aims to respond to the needs of adaptation to climate change at the local level and the reduction of the impact of increasingly persistent hazards such as the rising urban temperatures.</i>

Precondition	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Input data:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Air temperature data from thermo-hygrommetric sensor</i> ○ <i>Landsat 8 images</i> ○ <i>DSM, DTM</i> ● <i>Tools:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>tools to process landsat images (Google Earth Engine)</i> ○ <i>tools to process the sensor data and performing cokriging (R scripts)</i> ○ <i>visualization service connected with the geoserver of the municipality (leaflet)</i> 	
Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Data in Dashboard and Visualization service:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Raster data UHI Zaragoza:</i> https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/87091cb4-83b4-47c3-91bd-a7c8a5d9508f ● <i>Synthetic Socio-Climate Vulnerability Indicator:</i> https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/89ff898a-40c5-4d14-8914-17b90c1bed91
Use of DRI	<p>This DRI has been used for the data-driven decisions related to urbanism design. Additionally, it serves as justification for obtaining funding for projects focused on meeting the LGD.</p> <p>For example, the visualization service has been used to facilitate the selection of two schools within the initiative "Adapta tu patio"</p>
Use case processing steps	
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PDcIX7q6vUkkE4JntjkymUvQzOqt-2uy/view?usp=sharing	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15166758	